

STUDIES IN BACTERIAL AMYLASES. PART II. THE SOURCE OF CARBON AS A DETERMINANT IN AMYLASE FORMATION BY *B. SUBTILIS*

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The effect of different polysaccharides, sugars, sugar alcohols and salts of lactic acid, as sources of carbon have been studied. Starch yields the highest amount of the amylases, next in order come sucrose, dextrin, fructose, arabinose, glucose, mannose, maltose, mannitol, lactose, xylose, pectin, dulcitol and rhamninnose. Galactose, raffinose and inulin were found to be poor enzyme formers. Lactates do not form a good source of carbon.

During the studies on the nutritional requirements of diastase producing bacteria, it was found of great interest to investigate the suitable sources of nitrogen and carbon, playing a very important role in the formation of amylase. The work on the suitability of the various forms of nitrogen has already been described in the previous communication (Lulla, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 119). The present work therefore deals with the effect of different sources of carbon in relation to amylase formation in bacteria (*B. subtilis*, N. C. T. C., 2027 N). Brunton and Macfadyan (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1889, 46, B, 542) reported that amylase was produced in the case of two bacteria only when grown on starch and not on meat extract. Dox (*Bur. Animal Ind.*, Bull. No. 120, U. S. Dept., Agrl., 1910) postulated that the amount of carbohydrase elaborated could be materially increased by cultivating the organism on a particular substratum. This was found to be particularly true in the case of amylase, lactase and inulase, enzymes of fungal origin. Biodin and Effront (U. S. Patent 1,227,374, May 22, 1917) employed the starch or enzymatically digested starchy materials as a source of carbon for the growth of *B. subtilis* and *B. Mesentericus* in relation to amylase formation. The studies have also been conducted with the extracts of different naturally occurring materials, rich in carbohydrates by various workers (Tilden and Hudson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2139, 1432; Beckord, Kneen and Lewis, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, 37, 692) during their investigations on the amylase formation with different organisms. No where in the literature, comparative data regarding the efficiency of the different carbon sources employed for the cultivation of the diastase producing bacteria, using one single strain, has been observed. The present studies have therefore been made to find out the effect of the various sources of carbon on the formation of amylase. Among the various sources of carbon tried, the following classes of compounds have received attention.

1. Carbohydrates which includes: (a) Pentoses (arabinose and xylose); (b) Hexoses (glucose, mannose, fructose and galactose); (c) Disaccharides and trisaccharides (sucrose, maltose, lactose, rhamninnose and raffinose); (d) Polysaccharides (starch, dextrin, inulin and pectin); (e) Sugar alcohols (mannitol and dulcitol).
2. Lactates of sodium, potassium and calcium.

EXPERIMENTAL

During these studies the media of the following composition were employed in order to find out the effect of different sources of carbon on the formation of bacterial amylase.

Media composition.—Culture medium (10 ml.), previously adjusted to p_H 7.0, consisted of 1.0 ml. of basal medium (Lulla, *loc. cit.*), 1.0 ml. of ammonium lactate solution equivalent to 2.0 mg. level of nitrogen which served as a nitrogen source, and the carbon source which was variant during these investigations was added so as to give the final ratio of nitrogen to carbon as 1:13.

FIG. 1

Effect of starch and its hydrolytic compounds on the formation of amylase.

FIG. 2

Effect of diff. sugars on the formation of amylase.

FIG. 3

Effect of polysaccharides and sugar alcohols on the formation of amylase.

The methods of growing the bacteria and assaying the amylase activity have been described previously (Lulla, *loc. cit.*). The results obtained with various carbon sources are represented in the Figs. 1-3 and the units of amylase calculated per 10 ml. of the culture medium are also expressed in Table I.

TABLE I

Polysaccharides		Oligo saccharides		Monosaccharides	
Source of carbon.	*Enzyme unit.	Source of carbon.	*Enzyme unit.	Source of carbon.	*Enzyme unit.
Starch	112.5	Maltose	60.0	Glucose	69.2
Dextrin	80.0	Sucrose	94.7	Mannose	64.2
Inulin	Negligible	Lactose	50.0	Galactose	Negligible
Pectin	42.4	Raffinose	Negligible	Fructose	80.0
		Rhamnose	24.8	Arabinose	80.0
Lactates of				Xylose	47.4
sodium	Negligible				
potassium	Do			Sugar alcohol	
calcium	Do			Dulcitol	29.6
				Mannitol	51.4

*per 10 ml. of culture medium

DISCUSSION

Two sources of carbon which have been investigated fall into two broad groups:—

- The carbohydrates, which include a variety of pentoses, hexoses, di- and tri-saccharides, sugar alcohols and a few typical polysaccharides.
- The lactates of sodium, potassium and calcium.

So far as carbohydrate series is concerned, the most luxuriant growth of the bacteria and the highest yield of the enzyme are secured by providing starch as the source of carbon; on the other hand, the negligible quantity of the enzyme is formed when galactose, raffinose and inulin are respectively furnished as a source of carbon. The bacteria was seen to thrive with equal facility on most of the carbohydrates tried as on starch, but its efficiency regarding enzyme formation varied with the individual source of carbohydrate.

The lactates were tried because of the previous finding (Lulla, *loc. cit.*), that ammonium lactate furnished the best source of nitrogen, in the culture media. It was therefore suggested that lactate must constitute a very easily assimilable source of carbon. This expectation has not been realised as negligible quantity of the amylase is formed in case of lactates other than ammonium lactate. It must now be accepted that it is only as the ammonium salt that it exerts a very favourable effect on the formation of amylase.

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